

CODEN [USA]: IAJPBB

ISSN : 2349-7750

**INDO AMERICAN JOURNAL OF
PHARMACEUTICAL SCIENCES**

SJIF Impact Factor: 7.187

Available online at: <http://www.iajps.com>

Research Article

FORMULATION AND EVALUATION OF INVASOMAL GELK.Nikhita¹, Zeenath Ruty²¹Mother Teresa College of Pharmacy, N.F.C Nagar, Ghatkesar, Medchal, Telangana.**Article Received: October 2024 Accepted: November 2024 Published: December 2024****Abstract:**

Invasomes laden with ketoconazole were made by a thin-film hydration technique. Drug-to-lipid ratios (IG1 to IG7) were varied to create seven formulations. The produced formulations were assessed for in vitro drug release studies, drug content, entrapment efficiency, zeta potential, and particle size. The viscosity values of the formulations with the highest amount of carbopol 934P (1.0 g) were 589 cp, while the formulations with the lowest amount (0.2 g) were 345 cp. The Spreadability analysis reveals a similar trend, with a less gelling agent and a higher Spreadability. 934P had the lowest value when there was a lot of carbopol present. In the "Homogeneity" investigation, every formulation showed that there was no aggregated mass or clog mass. The IG4 formulation of Invasomes was deemed the best of all the formulations. A prolonged drug release of 76.9% was seen at 14 hours with the "IG4" formulation. SEM analysis showed that the invasomes were distributed widely.

Keywords: *Invasomes, thin-film hydration technique, gel, gelling agent, SEM analysis.***Corresponding author:****Zeenath Ruty***Mother Teresa College of Pharmacy, N.F.C Nagar,
Ghatkesar, Medchal, Telangana.*

QR code

Please cite this article in press **Zeenath Ruty et al Formulation And Evaluation Of Invasomal Gel**., *Indo Am. J. P. Sci*, 2024; 11 (12).

INTRODUCTION:

The transdermal delivery of drugs is rapidly increasing in formulation development in enhancing the bioavailability of many drugs. When drugs are administered via the transdermal route skin barrier is harmfully affected. In recent years, vesicular systems have been intensively studied as drug carrier systems for the dermal and transdermal administration of drugs [1]. Traditional liposomal formulations, compared to conventional dosage forms, have shown in vitro an enhanced cutaneous drug accumulation allowing a reduction of the dose applied onto the skin. In the last two decades, new classes of lipid vesicles were introduced by different researchers [2]. More recently, researchers investigated the novel vesicular systems called as invasomes. Briefly, invasomes contain not only phospholipids but also ethanol and terpenes, which make the vesicles deformable, and also serve as penetration enhancers [1=3]. This system has been shown to improve skin penetration of hydrophilic and lipophilic drugs. A synergistic effect between terpenes and ethanol on the percutaneous absorption has been significantly observed. In this study, we investigated the ability of invasomes to increase the topical transport of ketoconazole in order to develop a topical formulation with enhanced ketoconazole skin delivery to achieve an effective fungal treatment [4]. Ethanol is a good penetration enhancer while terpenes have also shown potential to increase the penetration of many drugs by disrupting the tight lipid packing of the stratum corneum [5]. The present study aimed to develop and characterize ketoconazole-loaded invasomal drug carrier systems. ketoconazole has been previously identified as a promising candidate for transdermal drug delivery

MATERIALS AND METHODS:

Ketoconazole was purchased from Natco Pharma Labs. Phosphatidylcholine, Carbopol-934, and Limonene were obtained from Research Lab Fine Chem. Industries (Mumbai).

METHODOLOGY:

$$EE = ((\text{Total drug} - \text{Drug in supernatant})) / (\text{Total drug}) \times 100$$

Surface morphology, Particle size, and zeta potential of optimized formulation:

Using a scanning electron microscope, the prepared Invasome's morphology was examined. A glass slide was placed on the sample after it had been spread out over the slab surface, and photomicrographs using a scanning electron microscope (S3700N-Hitachi,

FTIR study of Drug and Excipients:

FTIR spectroscopy is specifically used for online polymer composition monitoring. The ability of infrared to fingerprint chemical components allows for the identification of the substances involved in a chemical process. FTIR Bruker Opus 7.0, a German business, conducted the investigation [6].

Differential Scanning Calorimetry (DSC) study:

A thermal analysis tool called a DSC measures temperature and the changes in a sample's physical characteristics over time. The apparatus is a thermal analysis tool that measures the temperature and heat transfer related to material transitions as a function of temperature and time, to put it another way. Shimadzu, USA's DSC-60 performed DSC [7].

Invasome preparation technique:

Invasome made using the film hydration technique filled with ketoconazole. In ethanol, ketoconazole and phosphatidylcholine were dissolved. The solution was then treated in a rotary flask evaporator after being moved to a round bottom flask (RBF). To produce a dry RBF film, the mixture was subsequently thoroughly dried under vacuum at 40 °C, 100 rpm, and 16 mm Hg. After being at ambient temperature for two hours under vacuum (1 mbar), the film is flushed with nitrogen [8]. Next, the deposited film is hydrated using a phosphate buffer (pH: 6.8; PBS) mixture that contains ethanol and D-limonene for 30 minutes at lipid phase transition. To obtain varied invasome pore diameters, the resulting vesicles are vortexed and ultrasonically sonicated at 45% amplitude for 10 minutes after cooling to room temperature.

Characterization of Invasome:**Entrapment efficiency:**

For one hour at 4 °C, samples were centrifuged at 14,000 rpm to determine the amount of ketoconazole trapped in the produced invasomes [9]. After separation, the supernatant was measured quantitatively at $\lambda_{\text{max}} = 256 \text{ nm}$ using a UV spectrophotometer

Japan) were taken at various magnifications [10]. Similar to this, the scattering light intensity technique was used to assess the particle size and polydispersity index value of invasomes (Malvern zeta sizer, ATA scientific, USA).

Procedure for preparation of Gel loaded with

Invasome:

Carbopol 934P was put in a 100 ml beaker with lukewarm water. To prevent a lump from forming, mixing was done in a magnetic stirrer set to 50 RPM (Remi stirrer, Mumbai, India). The resulting liquid was mixed with the necessary amount of triethanolamine to bring the pH down and create the

gel. PEG 400, glycerol, and benzalkonium chloride were taken and well mixed in a different beaker. Invasome is appropriately blended and added to that mixture [11]. Lastly, a magnetic stirrer was used to stir the drug dispersion at 100 RPM after it had been placed into the Carbopol 934P gel.

Table 1: Gel formulation composition

Ingredients	IG1	IG2	IG3	IG4	IG5	IG6	IG7
Invasome – ml (Equal to 100 mg API)	5.0	5.0	5.0	5.0	5.0	5.0	5.0
Carbopol 934P (g)	0.1	0.3	0.5	0.7	0.9	1.1	1.3
PEG 600 (ml)	25.0	20.0	15.0	10.0	-	-	-
Glycerol (ml)	-	-	-	-	25.0	20.0	15.0
Triethanolamine (ml)	q.s.						
Purified water	q.s.						

Drug content:

100 millilitres of ethanolic phosphate buffer with a pH of 7.4 was used to dissolve a measured portion of the prepared gel. For an entire hour, the gel solution was constantly shaken with a mechanical shaker [12]. The resulting solution was filtered, and using phosphate buffer (pH 7.4) as a blank, it was spectrophotometrically examined at 256 nm using a UV-Visible spectrophotometer (Shimadzu UV-1800, Japan).

pH determination:

Using a digital pH meter (Systronic Digital, Model: 335, Mumbai), the gel's pH was measured.

Viscosity: To determine the viscosity of the produced gels, a Brookfield viscometer (model DV-II+Pro, USA) was utilised. Spindle No. 64 was utilised for this. The spindle was rotated at 50 rpm to record the viscosity [13].

Spreadability:

Glass slide equipment and a wooden block were used to gauge how easily the gels spread. The amount of created gel that was put in the pan was about 500 mg. The higher slide's separation time from the fixed slides was recorded [14]. The gel spreadability was assessed using the accompanying formula:

$$S=ML/T$$

Where S = spreadability, M = mass tied to upper slide, L = length of glass slide, T = time it takes for the slide to detach.

Homogeneity:

All created gel compositions were described in order to evaluate their homogeneity. This was accomplished through visual examination of the gel following its settlement in appropriate containers [15]. The look and presence of any clogs in the gels were examined.

In-vitro diffusion study:

Using a Franz-diffusion cell and the diffusion technique, ketoconazole was released from the gel in vitro. Before use, the dialysis and cellophane membranes were divided into equal parts (6 cm x 2.5 cm) and soaked in distilled water for 12 hrs. With a magnetic stirrer and continuous heating apparatus, the TC solution's drug release tests are conducted in 10 millilitres of phosphate buffer pH 6.8 saline that is kept at 37±0.5°. One gramme of the gel sample was put in the donor compartment. The same volume of fresh buffer was used to replace the 1 ml aliquot samples that were taken out at regular intervals. A UV spectrophotometer set to 256 nm was used to measure the amount of medication that diffused through the membrane.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION:**FTIR study:**

Figure 10 displays the usual characteristic peaks of the ketoconazole FTIR spectrum: O-H stretching at 3198.73 cm⁻¹, C-C stretching at 1498.45 to 1589.77 cm⁻¹, aryl C-N stretching at 1276.13 cm⁻¹, and C-F stretching at 1128.93 to 1050.43 cm⁻¹.

Figure 1: FTIR spectra of pure Ketoconazole

Differential Scanning Calorimetry (DSC) study

A sharp endothermic peak with a heat of energy of -361.96 mJ was recorded at 132.33 °C, in accordance with the literature analysis.

Figure 2: DSC of Ketoconazole

Characterization of Invasome

Table 2: % EE data

Run	% EE
T1	68.73±2.5
T2	64.58±1.8
T3	70.11±3.3
T4	62.73±2.9
T5	66.41±1.5
T6	73.29±2.2
T7	61.46±3.7

High EE was detected in formulations that contained a significant amount of phospholipid. Formulations "T6" and "T3" had maximum entrapment rates of 73.29%, 70.11% respectively.

Figure 3: FTIR spectra of D-limonene

Typical characteristic peaks may be seen in the stretching band of C=C at 1610.97 cm⁻¹ in the FTIR spectrum of D-limonene. Additionally, it observed a strong band at 2918.94 cm⁻¹, which is the valence vibration of the C–H bond in methylene. The double bonds in limonene are represented by the peaks that are seen at 1337.96, 1279.74, and 1121.70 cm⁻¹.

Figure 4: FTIR spectra of phosphatidylcholine

In the sample absorption is observed and verified carefully; there is a band near 3312.83 cm⁻¹ arising which can be assigned to OH stretching vibration. A prominent absorption band of CH for the nitrogen-bound methyl group appeared at 2922.16 cm⁻¹. In phosphate moiety, the band arising from the antisymmetric stretching vibration developed at 1041.00 cm⁻¹.

Figure 5: FTIR spectra of optimized formulation

It was detected that no important modifications occurred and that the peaks were in their typical locations. The optimal formulation's FTIR spectrum (Figure 8) displays typical characteristic peaks at 1128.11 to 1048.60 cm⁻¹ (C-F stretching), 1275.52 cm⁻¹ (aryl C-N stretching), 1497.63 to 1589.25 cm⁻¹ (C-C stretching), and 2923.88 cm⁻¹ (indicating O-H stretching).

Surface morphology, Particle size and zeta potential of optimized formulation

Figure 6: SEM study of Optimized formulation (5.0 μm)

SEM analysis revealed a dispersed distribution of invasomes. The optimized Invasome's surface and look were likewise found to be symmetrical by the study. As seen in Figure 6, invasive species are evenly distributed throughout the specimen.

202402021235005.nsz

Measurement Results

Date : 02 February 2024 12:35:39
 Measurement Type : Particle Size
 Sample Name : SIZE
 Scattering Angle : 90
 Temperature of the holder : 25.0 deg. C
 T% before meas. : 7511
 Viscosity of the dispersion medium : 0.895 mPa.s
 Form Of Distribution : Narrow
 Representation of result : Scattering Light Intensity
 Count rate : 1827 kCPS

Calculation Results

Peak No.	S.P.Area Ratio	Mean	S. D.	Mode
1	1.00	189.8 nm	46.6 nm	143.8 nm
2	—	— nm	— nm	— nm
3	—	— nm	— nm	— nm
Total	1.00	189.8 nm	46.6 nm	143.8 nm

Histogram Operations

Size (Median) : 159.9 nm
 Mode : 143.6 nm
 % Cumulative (1) : 5.0 (%) - 112.4 (nm)
 % Cumulative (2) : 10.0 (%) - 119.9 (nm)
 % Cumulative (3) : 20.0 (%) - 129.8 (nm)
 % Cumulative (4) : 30.0 (%) - 139.5 (nm)
 % Cumulative (5) : 40.0 (%) - 149.2 (nm)
 % Cumulative (6) : 50.0 (%) - 159.9 (nm)
 % Cumulative (7) : 60.0 (%) - 171.6 (nm)
 % Cumulative (8) : 70.0 (%) - 186.4 (nm)
 % Cumulative (9) : 80.0 (%) - 205.7 (nm)
 % Cumulative (10) : 90.0 (%) - 235.3 (nm)

Cumulant Operations

Z-Average : 191.8 nm
 PI : 0.397

Figure 7: Analysis of the optimised formulation's particle size and distribution

The optimised formulation's average size was found to be 159.9 nm by the particle size investigation. The value of the polydispersity index (PI) was also 0.397. The literature states that homogeneous dispersion is indicated by a PI value of less than 0.5. This shows that the invasomes in the formulation are uniformly distributed in size.

Measurement Results

202402021515006.nzt

Measurement Results

Date : 04 February 2024 15:15:01

Measurement Type : Zeta Potential

Sample Name : ZETA

Temperature of the holder : 25.0 deg. C

Viscosity of the dispersion medium : 0.895 mPa.s

Conductivity : 0.166 mS/cm

Electrode Voltage : 3.4 V

Calculation Results

Peak No.	Zeta Potential	Electrophoretic Mobility
1	-23.5 mV	-0.000182 cm ² /Vs
2	— mV	— cm ² /Vs
3	— mV	— cm ² /Vs

Zeta Potential (Mean) : -23.5 mV

Electrophoretic Mobility mean : -0.000182 cm²/Vs

1/1

Figure 8: Estimating the zeta potential of an optimised formulation

Zeta potential was measured for invasomes distributed in phosphate buffer with a pH of 6.8. The value above ± 15 mV is steady and can be distributed without causing stability problems, according to the literature review. According to the existing literature, the zeta value in our investigation was -23.5 mV, indicating stability.

DSC of study of optimized Invasome:

Figure 9: DSC thermogram of D-Limonene

D limonene exhibited characteristic boiling point peak at 229.44 °C which is as per literature review information provided. The characteristic peak indicated the purity of the sample.

Figure 10: DSC thermogram of Phospholipid

Phospholipid exhibited characteristic peak at 131.89 °C and a small intensity peak at 210.95 °C.

Figure 11: DSC thermogram of Optimized formulation Invasome

The sharp endothermal peak at 103.61 °C, which is close to pure ketoconazole based on the before observed value of 132.33 °C, was underlined by the DSC research. This determined the endothermal peak's non-significant alteration. The pure drug's thermal stability in the formulation was also deduced. It was stated that phospholipid did not exhibit such a noticeable peak. This might be because of the intermediate complex that the quaternary ammonium ion in the phospholipid and D-limonene that we looked at in our study formed.

Characterization of gels:

Table 3: Characterization of gels

Formulations	Characterization of gels				
	Drug content (%)	pH	Viscosity(cp)	Spreadability (mm)	Homogeneity
IG1	87.1±6.0	6.4±0.1	341±6	84±1.5	+++
IG2	82.0±4.7	6.6±0.3	412±8	58±1.4	+++
IG3	86.5±3.8	6.8±0.2	435±7	66±1.7	++
IG4	91.3±5.7	6.5±0.4	587±4	47±1.6	++
IG5	83.5±3.1	6.6±0.3	421±8	77±1.2	+++
IG6	86.2±1.5	6.7±0.2	465±2	72±1.3	+++
IG7	91.3±1.3	7.2±0.4	534±4	61±1.1	++

For all data, the mean ± standard error of mean (n = 3) is used.

The drug content varied from 83.1% to 92.4% in all formulations, as shown in Table 21. These variations in pH values, which are within the typical range of the skin, were not seen. The determined range of viscosity was 345 cp to 589 cp. The formulations containing the most carbopol 934P had the greatest viscosity value. The Spreadability investigation shows a similar pattern. All of the formulations in the "Homogeneity" investigation demonstrated the nonappearance of accumulated mass and clog mass.

In-vitro diffusion study:

Table 4: *In-vitro* dissolution study of gels (percentage drug release)

Time (Hour)	Formulations (Gel loaded with optimized Invasome)						
	IG1	IG2	IG3	IG4	IG5	IG6	IG7
0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
1	37.2±4.7	26.8±5.1	23.6±2.6	16.8±3.5	33.8±4.2	24.6±5.2	16.4±4.2
2	52.6±6.1	42.5±6.2	34.1±3.5	26.4±6.2	49.1±5.5	38.7±4.5	26.1±5.3
4	64.1±3.9	58.1±4.6	47.8±6.1	32.9±4.5	60.5±3.7	49.2±2.7	40.5±6.2
6	77.3±5.5	66.7±3.2	53.6±5.2	48.4±4.7	71.8±1.8	57.1±5.3	48.7±2.7
8	88.6±6.1	71.1±5.6	68.2±4.4	53.2±2.8	82.9±3.7	62.7±1.9	61.3±4.6
10	99.8±4.4	87.9±6.1	85.4±3.7	65.5±5.1	91.5±2.8	72.6±3.4	72.5±5.2
12		99.1±4.4	98.3±6.2	68.6±3.3	98.4±4.5	85.4±5.8	78.1±4.9
14				76.9±6.3			80.6±5.5

Figure 12: *In-vitro* dissolution study of gels loaded with optimized invasome

At 14 hours, the "IG4" formulation showed a longer drug release of 76.9%. Nevertheless, it is evident that "IG7" released 80.6% at 14 hours using 0.6g of carbopol 934P. Compared to gels with an equivalent quantity of PEG 600, the gels loaded with glycerol displayed delayed drug release. In contrast to IG7, which released 80.6% of the medication, IG3 released 98.3%.

FTIR study of best gel (IG4) formulation:

Figure 13: FTIR spectra of Carbopol 934 P

The FTIR spectrum of carbopol 934 P showed bands at 3095-3319 representing O-H stretching vibration. Similarly, a strong and intense intramolecular H-bonded and 1708.86 cm^{-1} for carbonyl stretching was observed.

Figure 14: FTIR spectra of best gel (IG4) loaded with optimized Invasome.

The FTIR spectrum of best gel (Figure 38) displays distinctive peaks at 3327.73 cm^{-1} (revealing of O-H stretching), 2115.69 cm^{-1} (C-C stretching), and at 1638.18 cm^{-1} (C-F stretching). It concluded that, the major peaks contributed for Ketoconazole are all present in our formulation which indicates the stability of developed gel.

DSC study :

Figure 15: DSC thermogram of best gel-IG4

DSC study highlighted a sharp endothermic peak at 104.18 °C, slightly deviating from the pure Ketoconazole as recorded earlier value of 132.33. This ascertained a significant change in endothermic peak and indicated mild interaction with excipients considered in this study.

SUMMARY AND CONCLUSION:

A thin film hydration technique was used to create ketoconazole-loaded invasomes. Different medication to fat ratios (IG1 to IG7) were used to create seven different formulations. Particle size, zeta potential, drug content, entrapment efficiency, and in vitro drug release tests were all assessed for the produced formulations. The IG4 formulation was thought to be the best of all the Invasome formulations. The "IG4" formulation had a prolonged drug release of 76.9% at 14 hours.

REFERENCES:

1. Dragicevic, N.; Verma, D.D.; Fahr, A. Invasomes: Vesicles for enhanced skin delivery of drugs. In *Percutaneous Penetration Enhancers Chemical Methods in Penetration Enhancement*; Springer: Berlin, Germany, 2016; pp. 77–92.
2. P. K. Lakshmi, B. Kalpana, D. Prasanthi. Invasomes-novel Vesicular Carriers for Enhanced Skin Permeation. *Systematic Reviews in Pharmacy*, 2013, 4(1), 26-30.
3. Uzma Afreen, A. Krishna Shailaja. Overall Review on Invasomes. *Research Journal of Nanoscience and Engineering*, 3 (4), 2019, 5-9.
4. Kumar, L.; Verma, S.; Singh, K.; Prasad, D.; Jain, A. Ethanol Based Vesicular Carriers in Transdermal Drug Delivery: Nanoethosomes and Transethosomes in Focus. *NanoWorld J.* 2016, 2, 41–51.
5. Kamran, M.; Ahad, A.; Aqil, M.; Imam, S.S.; Sultana, Y.; Ali, A. Design, formulation and optimization of novel soft nano-carriers for transdermal olmesartan medoxomil delivery: In vitro characterization and in vivo pharmacokinetic assessment. *Int. J. Pharm.* 2016, 505, 147–158.
6. Zhou, W.; He, S.; Yang, Y.; Jian, D.; Chen, X.; Ding, J. Formulation, characterization and clinical evaluation of propranolol hydrochloride gel for transdermal treatment of superficial infantile hemangioma. *Drug Dev. Ind. Pharm.* 2015, 41, 1109–1119.
7. Ohradanova-Repic, A.; Nogueira, E.; Hartl, I.; Gomes, A.C.; Preto, A.; Steinhuber, E.; Mühlgrabner, V.; Repic, M.; Kuttke, M.; Zwirzitz, A. Fab antibody fragment-functionalized liposomes for specific targeting of antigen-positive cells. *Nanomed. Nanotechnol. Biol. Med.* 2018, 14, 123–130.
8. Karimi, N.; Ghanbarzadeh, B.; Hamishehkar, H.; Keivani, F.; Pezeshki, A.; Gholian, M.M. Phytosome and liposome: The beneficial encapsulation systems in drug delivery and food application. *Appl. Food Biotechnol.* 2015, 2, 17–27.
9. Gauhar R. Qadri, Abdul Ahad, Mohd. Aqil, Syed S. Imam & Asgar Ali. Invasomes of isradipine for enhanced transdermal delivery against hypertension: formulation, characterization, and in-vivo pharmacodynamic study, *Artificial Cells, Nanomedicine, and Biotechnology*, 2017. 45:1, 139-145,
10. Thanaporn Amnuaitkit, Tunyaluk Limsuwana, Pasarat Khongkowb, Prapaporn Boonme.

- Vesicular carriers containing phenylethyl resorcinol for topical delivery system; liposomes, transfersomes and invasomes. *Asian Journal of Pharmaceutical Sciences*. 2018. 13,472–484.
11. Chaurasiya P., Ganju E., Upmanyu N., Ray S.K., Jain P. Transfersomes: A novel technique for transdermal drug delivery. *J. Drug Deliv. Ther.* 2019;9:279–285.
 12. Bhasin B., Londhe V.Y. An overview of transfersomal drug delivery. *Int. J. Pharm. Sci. Res.* 2018;9:2175–2184.
doi: 10.13040/IJPSR.0975-8232.9(6).2175-84.
 13. Kim B., Cho H.-E., Moon S.H., Ahn H.-J., Bae S., Cho H.-D., An S. Transdermal delivery systems in cosmetics. *Biomed. Dermatol.* 2020;4:1–12. doi: 10.1186/s41702-019-0053-z
 14. Jiang T., Wang T., Li T., Ma Y., Shen S., He B., Mo R. Enhanced transdermal drug delivery by transfersome-embedded oligopeptide hydrogel for topical chemotherapy of melanoma. *ACS Nano*. 2018;12:9693–9701.
 15. Sivannarayana P., Rani A.P., Saikishore V., VenuBabu C., SriRekha V. Transfersomes: Ultra deformable vesicular carrier systems in transdermal drug delivery system. *Res. J. Pharm. Dos. Forms Technol.* 2012;4:243–255.